

Neutrosophic \aleph –interior ideals in semigroups

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Abstract: We define the concepts of neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal and neutrosophic \aleph –characteristic interior ideal structures of a semigroup. We infer different types of semigroups using neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal structures. We also show that the intersection of neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideals and the union of neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideals is also a neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal.

Keywords: Semi group, neutrosophic \aleph –ideals, neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideals, neutrosophic \aleph –product.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, the theory of uncertainty plays a vital role to manage different issues relating to modelling engineering problems, networking, real-life problem relating to decision making and so on. In 1965, Zadeh[24] introduced the idea of fuzzy sets for modelling vague concepts in the globe. In 1986, Atanassov [1] generalized fuzzy set and named as Intuitionistic fuzzy set. Also, from his viewpoint, there are two degrees of freedom in the real world, one a degree of membership to a vague subset and the other is a degree of non-membership to that given subset.

Smarandache generalized fuzzy set and intuitionistic fuzzy set, and named as neutrosophic set (see [4, 7, 8, 14, 19, 22-23]). These sets are characterized by a truth membership function, an indeterminacy membership function and a falsity membership function. These sets are applied to many branches of mathematics to overcome the complexities arising from uncertain data. A Neutrosophic set can distinguish between absolute membership and relative membership. Smarandache used this in non-standard analysis such as the result of sports games (winning/defeating/tie), decision making and control theory, etc. This area has been studied by several authors (see [3, 11, 12, 16-18]).

For more details on neutrosophic set theory, the readers visit the website <http://fs.gallup.unm.edu/FlorentinSmarandache.htm>

In [2], Abdel Basset et al. designed a framework to manage scheduling problems using neutrosophic theory. As the concept of time-cost tradeoffs and deterministic project scheduling disagree with the real situation, some data were changed during the implementation process. Here fuzzy scheduling and time-cost tradeoffs models assumed only truth-membership functions dealing

with uncertainties of the project and their activities duration which were unable to treat indeterminacy and inconsistency.

In [6], Abdel Basset et al. evaluated the performance of smart disaster response systems under uncertainty. In [5], Abdel Basset et al. introduced different hybrid neutrosophic multi-criteria decision-making framework for professional selection that employed a collection of neutrosophic analytical network process and order preference by similarity to the ideal solution under bipolar neutrosophic numbers.

In [21], Prakasam Muralikrishna1 et al. presented the characterization of MBJ – Neutrosophic β – Ideal of β – algebra. They analyzed homomorphic image, pre-image, cartesian product and related results, and these concepts were explored to other substructures of a β – algebra. In [9], Chalapathi et al. constructed certain Neutrosophic Boolean rings, introduced Neutrosophic complement elements and mainly obtained some properties satisfied by the Neutrosophic complement elements of Neutrosophic Boolean rings.

In [14], M. Khan et al. presented the notion of neutrosophic \aleph -subsemigroup in semigroup and explored several properties. In [11], Gulistan et al. have studied the idea of complex neutrosophic subsemigroups and introduced the concept of the characteristic function of complex neutrosophic sets, direct product of complex neutrosophic sets.

In [10], B. Elavarasan et al. introduced the notion of neutrosophic \aleph -ideal in semigroup and explored its properties. Also, the conditions for neutrosophic \aleph -structure to be neutrosophic \aleph -ideal are given, and discussed the idea of characteristic neutrosophic \aleph -structure in semigroups and obtained several properties. In [20], we have introduced and discussed several properties of neutrosophic \aleph -bi-ideal in the semigroup. We have proved that neutrosophic \aleph -product and the intersection of neutrosophic \aleph -ideals were identical for regular semigroups. In this paper, we define and discuss the concepts of neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal and neutrosophic \aleph -characteristic interior ideal structures of a semigroup.

Throughout this paper, X denotes a semigroup. Now, we present the important definitions of semigroup that we need in sequel.

Recall that for any $X_1, X_2 \subseteq X$, $X_1 X_2 = \{ab | a \in X_1 \text{ and } b \in X_2\}$, multiplication of X_1 and X_2 .

Let X be a semigroup and $\emptyset \neq X_1 \subseteq X$. Then

- (i) X_1 is known as subsemigroup if $X_1^2 \subseteq X_1$.
- (ii) A subsemigroup X_1 is known as left (resp., right) ideal if $X_1 X \subseteq X_1$ (resp., $XX_1 \subseteq X_1$).
- (iii) X_1 is known as ideal if X_1 is both a left and a right ideal.
- (iv) X is known as left (resp., right) regular if for each $r \in X$, there exists $i \in X$ such that $r = ir^2$ (resp., $r = r^2i$) [13].
- (v) X is known as regular if for each $b_1 \in X$, there exists $i \in X$ such that $b_1 = b_1 i b_1$
- (vi) X is known as intra-regular if for each $x_1 \in X$, there exist $i, j \in X$ such that $x_1 = i x_1^2 j$ [15].

2. Definitions of neutrosophic \aleph - structures

We present definitions of neutrosophic \aleph – structures namely neutrosophic \aleph – subsemigroup, neutrosophic \aleph – ideal, neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideal of a semigroup X

The set of all the functions from X to $[-1, 0]$ is denoted by $\mathfrak{S}(X, [-1, 0])$. We call that an element of $\mathfrak{S}(X, [-1, 0])$ is \aleph -function on X . A \aleph -structure means an ordered pair (X, g) of X and an \aleph -function g on X .

Definition 2.1.[14] A neutrosophic \aleph -structure of X is defined to be the structure:

$$X_M := \frac{X}{(T_M, I_M, F_M)} = \left\{ \frac{r}{(T_M(r), I_M(r), F_M(r))} \mid r \in X \right\},$$

where T_M, I_M and F_M are the negative truth, negative indeterminacy and negative falsity membership function on X (\aleph -functions).

It is evident that $-3 \leq T_M(r) + I_M(r) + F_M(r) \leq 0$ for all $r \in X$.

Definition 2.2.[14] A neutrosophic \aleph -structure X_M of X is called a neutrosophic \aleph -subsemigroup of X if the following assertion is valid:

$$(\forall g_i, h_j \in X) \begin{pmatrix} T_M(g_i h_j) \leq T_M(g_i) \vee T_M(h_j) \\ I_M(g_i h_j) \geq I_M(g_i) \wedge I_M(h_j) \\ F_M(g_i h_j) \leq F_M(g_i) \vee F_M(h_j) \end{pmatrix}.$$

.Let X_M be a neutrosophic \aleph -structure and $\gamma, \delta, \epsilon \in [-1, 0]$ with $-3 \leq \gamma + \delta + \epsilon \leq 0$. Consider the sets:

$$\begin{aligned} T_M^\gamma &= \{r_i \in X \mid T_M(r_i) \leq \gamma\} \\ I_M^\delta &= \{r_i \in X \mid I_M(r_i) \geq \delta\} \\ F_M^\epsilon &= \{r_i \in X \mid F_M(r_i) \leq \epsilon\}. \end{aligned}$$

The set $X_M(\gamma, \delta, \epsilon) := \{r_i \in X \mid T_M(r_i) \leq \gamma, I_M(r_i) \geq \delta, F_M(r_i) \leq \epsilon\}$ is known as $(\gamma, \delta, \epsilon)$ -level set of X_M . It is easy to observe that $X_M(\gamma, \delta, \epsilon) = T_M^\gamma \cap I_M^\delta \cap F_M^\epsilon$.

Definition 2.3.[10] A neutrosophic \aleph -structure X_M of X is called a neutrosophic \aleph -left (resp., right) ideal of X if

$$(\forall g_i, h_j \in X) \begin{pmatrix} T_M(g_i h_j) \leq T_M(h_j) \text{ (resp., } T_M(g_i h_j) \leq T_M(g_i)) \\ I_M(g_i h_j) \geq I_M(h_j) \text{ (resp., } I_M(g_i h_j) \geq I_M(g_i)) \\ F_M(g_i h_j) \leq F_M(h_j) \text{ (resp., } F_M(g_i h_j) \leq F_M(g_i)) \end{pmatrix}.$$

X_M is neutrosophic \aleph -ideal of X if X_M is neutrosophic \aleph -left and \aleph -right ideal of X .

Definition 2.4. A neutrosophic \aleph -subsemigroup X_M of X is known as neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal if

$$(\forall x, a, y \in X) \begin{pmatrix} T_M(xay) \leq T_M(a) \\ I_M(xay) \geq I_M(a) \\ F_M(xay) \leq F_M(a) \end{pmatrix}.$$

It is easy to observe that every neutrosophic \aleph -ideal is neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal, but neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal need not be a neutrosophic \aleph -ideal, as shown by an example.

Example 2.5. Let X be the set of all non-negative integers except 1. Then X is a semigroup with usual multiplication.

Let $X_M = \left\{ \frac{0}{(-0.9, -0.1, -0.7)}, \frac{2}{(-0.4, -0.6, -0.5)}, \frac{5}{(-0.3, -0.8, -0.3)}, \frac{10}{(-0.3, -0.8, -0.1)}, \frac{\text{otherwise}}{(-0.7, -0.4, -0.6)} \right\}$. Then X_M is neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal, but not neutrosophic \aleph -ideal with $T_M(2.5) = -0.3 \not\leq T_M(2)$.

Definition 2.6.[14] For any $E \subseteq X$, the characteristic neutrosophic \aleph -structure is defined as

$$\chi_E(X_M) = \frac{X}{(\chi_E(T)_M, \chi_E(I)_M, \chi_E(F)_M)}$$

where

$$\chi_E(T)_M: X \rightarrow [-1, 0], r \rightarrow \begin{cases} -1 & \text{if } r \in E \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$$\chi_E(I)_M: X \rightarrow [-1, 0], r \rightarrow \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } r \in E \\ -1 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$$\chi_E(F)_M: X \rightarrow [-1, 0], r \rightarrow \begin{cases} -1 & \text{if } r \in E \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.7.[14] Let $X_N := \frac{X}{(T_N, I_N, F_N)}$ and $X_M := \frac{X}{(T_M, I_M, F_M)}$ be neutrosophic \aleph -structures of X . Then

- (i) X_N is called a neutrosophic \aleph -substructure of X_M , denote by $X_M \subseteq X_N$, if $T_M(r) \geq T_N(r)$, $I_M(r) \leq I_N(r)$, $F_M(r) \geq F_N(r)$ for all $r \in X$.
- (ii) If $X_N \subseteq X_M$ and $X_M \subseteq X_N$, then we say that $X_N = X_M$.
- (iii) The neutrosophic \aleph -product of X_N and X_M is defined to be a neutrosophic \aleph -structure of X ,

$$X_N \odot X_M := \frac{X}{(T_{N \circ M}, I_{N \circ M}, F_{N \circ M})} = \left\{ \frac{h}{(T_{N \circ M}(h), I_{N \circ M}(h), F_{N \circ M}(h))} \mid h \in X \right\},$$

where

$$(T_N \circ T_M)(h) = T_{N \circ M}(h) = \begin{cases} \bigwedge_{h=rs} \{T_N(r) \vee T_M(s)\} & \text{if } \exists r, s \in X \text{ such that } h = rs \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$$(I_N \circ I_M)(h) = I_{N \circ M}(h) = \begin{cases} \bigvee_{h=rs} \{I_N(r) \wedge I_M(s)\} & \text{if } \exists u, v \in X \text{ such that } h = rs \\ -1 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$$(F_N \circ F_M)(h) = F_{N \circ M}(h) = \begin{cases} \bigwedge_{h=rs} \{F_N(r) \vee F_M(s)\} & \text{if } \exists u, v \in X \text{ such that } h = rs \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

For $i \in X$, the element $\frac{i}{(T_{N \circ M}(i), I_{N \circ M}(i), F_{N \circ M}(i))}$ is simply denoted by $(X_N \odot X_M)(i) = (T_{N \circ M}(i), I_{N \circ M}(i), F_{N \circ M}(i))$.

- (iii) The union of X_N and X_M , a neutrosophic \aleph -structure over X is defined as

$$X_N \cup X_M = X_{N \cup M} = (X; T_{N \cup M}, I_{N \cup M}, F_{N \cup M}),$$

where

$$(T_N \cup T_M)(h_i) = T_{N \cup M}(h_i) = T_N(h_i) \wedge T_M(h_i),$$

$$(I_N \cup I_M)(h_i) = I_{N \cup M}(h_i) = I_N(h_i) \vee I_M(h_i),$$

$$(F_N \cup F_M)(h_i) = F_{N \cup M}(h_i) = F_N(h_i) \wedge F_M(h_i) \quad \forall h_i \in X.$$

- (iv) The intersection of X_N and X_M , a neutrosophic \aleph -structure over X is defined as

$$X_N \cap X_M = X_{N \cap M} = (X; T_{N \cap M}, I_{N \cap M}, F_{N \cap M}),$$

where

$$(T_N \cap T_M)(h_i) = T_{N \cap M}(h_i) = T_N(h_i) \vee T_M(h_i),$$

$$(I_N \cap I_M)(h_i) = I_{N \cap M}(h_i) = I_N(h_i) \wedge I_M(h_i),$$

$$(F_N \cap F_M)(h_i) = F_{N \cap M}(h_i) = F_N(h_i) \vee F_M(h_i) \quad \forall h_i \in X.$$

3. Neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideals

We study different properties of neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideals of X . It is evident that neutrosophic \aleph -ideal is a neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal of X , but not the converse. Further, for a regular and for an intra-regular semigroup, every neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal is neutrosophic \aleph -ideal.

All throughout this part, we consider X_M and X_N are neutrosophic \aleph – structures of X .

Theorem 3.1. For any $L \subseteq X$, the equivalent assertions are:

- (i) L is an interior ideal,
- (ii) The characteristic neutrosophic \aleph – structure $\chi_L(X_N)$ is a neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideal.

Proof: Suppose L is an interior ideal and let $x, a, y \in X$.

If $a \in L$, then $xay \in L$, so $\chi_L(T)_N(xay) = -1 = \chi_L(T)_N(a)$, $\chi_L(I)_N(xay) = 0 = \chi_L(I)_N(a)$ and $\chi_L(F)_N(xay) = -1 = \chi_L(F)_N(a)$.

If $a \notin L$, then $\chi_L(T)_N(xay) \leq 0 = \chi_L(T)_N(a)$, $\chi_L(I)_N(xay) \geq -1 = \chi_L(I)_N(a)$ and $\chi_L(F)_N(xay) \leq 0 = \chi_L(F)_N(a)$.

Therefore $\chi_L(X_N)$ is a neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideal.

Conversely, assume that $\chi_L(X_N)$ is a neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideal. Let $u \in L$ and $x, y \in X$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_L(T)_N(xuy) &\leq \chi_L(T)_N(u) = -1, \\ \chi_L(I)_N(xuy) &\geq \chi_L(I)_N(u) = 0, \\ \chi_L(F)_N(xuy) &\leq \chi_L(F)_N(u) = -1. \end{aligned}$$

So $xuy \in L$. □

Theorem 3.2. If X_M and X_N are neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideals, then $X_{M \cap N}$ is neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideal.

Proof: Let X_M and X_N be neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideals. For any $r, s, t \in X$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_{M \cap N}(rst) &= T_M(rst) \vee T_N(rst) \leq T_M(s) \vee T_N(s) = T_{M \cap N}(s), \\ I_{M \cap N}(rst) &= I_M(rst) \wedge I_N(rst) \geq I_M(s) \wedge I_N(s) = I_{M \cap N}(s), \\ F_{M \cap N}(rst) &= F_M(rst) \vee F_N(rst) \leq F_M(s) \vee F_N(s) = F_{M \cap N}(s). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $X_{M \cap N}$ is neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideal. □

Corollary 3.3. The arbitrary intersection of neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideals is a neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideal.

Theorem 3.4. If X_M and X_N are neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideals, then $X_{M \cup N}$ is neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideal.

Proof: Let X_M and X_N be neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideals. For any $r, s, t \in X$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_{M \cup N}(rst) &= T_M(rst) \wedge T_N(rst) \leq T_M(s) \wedge T_N(s) = T_{M \cup N}(s), \\ I_{M \cup N}(rst) &= I_M(rst) \vee I_N(rst) \geq I_M(s) \vee I_N(s) = I_{M \cup N}(s), \\ F_{M \cup N}(rst) &= F_M(rst) \wedge F_N(rst) \leq F_M(s) \wedge F_N(s) = F_{M \cup N}(s). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $X_{M \cup N}$ is neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideal. □

Corollary 3.5. The arbitrary union of neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideals is neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideal.

Theorem 3.6. Let X be a regular semigroup. If X_M is neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideal, then X_M is neutrosophic \aleph – ideal.

Proof: Assume that X_M is an interior ideal, and let $u, v \in X$. As X is regular and $u \in X$, there exists $r \in X$ such that $u = uru$. Now, $T_M(uv) = T_M(uruv) \leq T_M(u)$, $I_M(uv) = I_M(uruv) \geq I_M(u)$ and $F_M(uv) = F_M(uruv) \leq F_M(u)$. Therefore X_M is neutrosophic \aleph – right ideal.

Similarly, we can show that X_M is neutrosophic \aleph – left ideal and hence X_M is neutrosophic \aleph – ideal. □

Theorem 3.7. Let X be an intra-regular semigroup. If X_M is neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideal, then X_M is neutrosophic \aleph – ideal.

Proof: Suppose that X_M is neutrosophic \aleph – interior ideal, and let $u, v \in X$. As X is intra regular and $u \in X$, there exist $s, t \in S$ such that $u = su^2t$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned} T_M(uv) &= T_M(su^2tv) \leq T_M(u), \\ I_M(uv) &= I_M(su^2tv) \geq I_M(u) \\ F_M(uv) &= F_M(su^2tv) \leq F_M(u). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore X_M is neutrosophic \aleph – right ideal. similarly, we can show that X_M is neutrosophic \aleph – left ideal and hence X_M is neutrosophic \aleph – ideal. □

Definition 3.8. A semigroup X is left simple (resp., right simple) if it does not contain any proper left ideal (resp., right ideal) of X . A semigroup X is simple if it does not contain any proper ideal of X .

Definition 3.9. A semigroup X is said to be neutrosophic \aleph –simple if every neutrosophic \aleph – ideal is a constant function

i.e., for every neutrosophic \aleph –ideal X_M of X , we have $T_M(i) = T_M(j)$, $I_M(i) = I_M(j)$ and $F_M(i) = F_M(j)$ for all $i, j \in X$.

Notation 3.10. If X is a semigroup and $s \in X$, we define a subset, denoted by I_s as follows:

$$I_s := \{i \in X \mid T_N(i) \leq T_N(s), I_N(i) \geq I_N(s) \text{ and } F_N(i) \leq F_N(s)\}.$$

Proposition 3.11. If X_N is neutrosophic \aleph – right (resp., \aleph – left, \aleph – ideal) ideal, then I_s is right (resp., left, ideal) ideal for every $s \in X$.

Proof: Let $s \in X$. Then it is clear that $\varphi \neq I_s \subseteq X$. Let $u \in I_s$ and $x \in X$. Then $ux \in I_s$. Indeed; Since X_N is neutrosophic \aleph – right ideal and $u, x \in X$, we get $T_N(ux) \leq T_N(u)$, $I_N(ux) \geq I_N(u)$ and $F_N(ux) \leq F_N(t)$. Since $u \in I_s$, we get $T_N(u) \leq T_N(s)$, $I_N(u) \geq I_N(s)$ and $F_N(u) \leq F_N(s)$ which imply $ux \in I_s$. Therefore I_s is a right ideal for every $s \in X$. □

Theorem 3.12.[4] For any $L \subseteq X$, the equivalent assertions are:

- (i) L is left (resp., right) ideal,
- (ii) Characteristic neutrosophic \aleph –structure $\chi_L(X_N)$ is neutrosophic \aleph –left (resp., right) ideal.

Theorem 3.13. Let X be a semigroup. Then X is simple if and only if X is neutrosophic \aleph –simple.

Proof: Suppose X is simple. Let X_M be a neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -ideal and $u, v \in X$. Then by Proposition 3.11, I_u is an ideal of X . As X is simple, we have $I_u = X$. Since $v \in I_u$, we have $T_M(v) \leq T_M(u)$, $I_M(v) \geq I_M(u)$ and $F_M(v) \leq F_M(u)$.

Similarly, we can prove that $T_M(u) \leq T_M(v)$, $I_M(u) \geq I_M(v)$ and $F_M(u) \leq F_M(v)$. So $T_M(u) = T_M(v)$, $I_M(u) = I_M(v)$ and $F_M(u) = F_M(v)$. Hence X is neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -simple.

Conversely, assume that X is neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -simple and I is an ideal of X . Then by Theorem 3.12, $\chi_I(X_N)$ is a neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -ideal. We now claim that $X = I$. Let $w \in X$. Since X is neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -simple, we have $\chi_I(X_N)$ is a constant function and $\chi_I(X_N)(w) = \chi_I(X_N)(y)$ for every $y \in X$. In particular, we have $\chi_I(T_N)(w) = \chi_I(T_N)(d) = -1$, $\chi_I(I_N)(w) = \chi_I(I_N)(d) = 0$ and $\chi_I(F_N)(w) = \chi_I(F_N)(d) = -1$ for any $d \in I$ which implies $w \in I$. Thus $X \subseteq I$ and hence $X = I$. \square

Lemma 3.14. Let X be a semigroup. Then X is simple if and only for every $t \in X$, we have $X = XtX$.

Proof: Suppose X is simple and let $t \in X$. Then $X(XtX) \subseteq XtX$ and $(XtX)X \subseteq XtX$ imply that XtX is an ideal. Since X is simple, we have $XtX = X$.

Conversely, let P be an ideal and let $a \in P$. Then $X = XaX$, $XaX \subseteq XPX \subseteq P$ which implies $P = X$. Therefore X is simple. \square

Theorem 3.15. Suppose X is a semigroup. Then X is simple if and only every neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -interior ideal of X is a constant function.

Proof: Suppose X is simple and $s, t \in X$. Let X_N be neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -interior ideal. Then by Lemma 3.14, we get $X = XsX = XtX$. As $s \in XsX$, we have $s = atb$ for $a, b \in X$. Since X_N is neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -interior ideal, we have $T_N(s) = T_N(atb) \leq T_N(t)$, $I_N(s) = I_N(atb) \geq I_N(t)$ and $F_N(s) = F_N(atb) \leq F_N(t)$. Similarly, we can prove that $T_N(t) \leq T_N(s)$, $I_N(t) \geq I_N(s)$ and $F_N(t) \leq F_N(s)$. So X_N is a constant function.

Conversely, suppose X_N is neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -ideal. Then X_N is neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -interior ideal. By hypothesis, X_N is a constant function and so X_N is neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -simple. By Theorem 3.13, X is simple. \square

Theorem 3.16. Let X_M be neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -structure and let $\gamma, \delta, \epsilon \in [-1, 0]$ with $-3 \leq \gamma + \delta + \epsilon \leq 0$. If X_M is neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -interior ideal, then $(\gamma, \delta, \epsilon)$ -level set of X_M is neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -interior ideal whenever $X_M(\gamma, \delta, \epsilon) \neq \emptyset$.

Proof: Suppose $X_M(\gamma, \delta, \epsilon) \neq \emptyset$ for $\gamma, \delta, \epsilon \in [-1, 0]$ with $-3 \leq \gamma + \delta + \epsilon \leq 0$.

Let X_M be a neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -interior ideal and let $u, v, w \in X_M(\gamma, \delta, \epsilon)$. Then $T_M(uvw) \leq T_M(v) \leq \alpha$; $I_M(uvw) \geq I_M(v) \geq \beta$ and $F_M(uvw) \leq F_M(v) \leq \gamma$ which imply $uvw \in X_M(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$. Therefore $X_M(\gamma, \delta, \epsilon)$ is a neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -interior ideal of X . \square

Theorem 3.17. Let X_N be neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -structure with $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [-1, 0]$ such that $-3 \leq \alpha + \beta + \gamma \leq 0$. If T_N^α , I_N^β and F_N^γ are interior ideals, then X_N is neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -interior ideal of X whenever it is non-empty.

Proof: Suppose that for $a, b, c \in X$ with $T_N(abc) > T_N(b)$. Then $T_N(abc) > t_\alpha \geq T_N(b)$ for some $t_\alpha \in [-1, 0)$. So $b \in T_N^{t_\alpha}(b)$ but $abc \notin T_N^{t_\alpha}(b)$, a contradiction. Thus $T_N(abc) \leq T_N(b)$.

Suppose that for $a, b, c \in X$ with $I_N(abc) < I_N(b)$. Then $I_N(abc) < t_\alpha \leq I_N(b)$ for some $t_\alpha \in [-1, 0)$. So $b \in I_N^{t_\alpha}(b)$ but $abc \notin I_N^{t_\alpha}(b)$, a contradiction. Thus $I_N(abc) \geq I_N(b)$.

Suppose that for $a, b, c \in X$ with $F_N(abc) > F_N(b)$. Then $F_N(abc) > t_\alpha \geq F_N(b)$ for some $t_\alpha \in [-1, 0)$. So $b \in F_N^{t_\alpha}(b)$ but $abc \notin F_N^{t_\alpha}(b)$, a contradiction. Thus $F_N(abc) \leq F_N(b)$.

Thus X_N is neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal. □

Theorem 3.18. Let X_M be neutrosophic \aleph -structure over X . Then the equivalent assertions are:

- (i) X_M is neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal,
- (ii) $X_N \odot X_M \odot X_N \subseteq X_M$ for any neutrosophic \aleph -structure X_N .

Proof: Suppose X_M is neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal. Let $x \in X$. For any $u, v, w \in X$ such that $x = uvw$. Then $T_M(x) = T_M(uvw) \leq T_M(v) \leq T_N(u) \vee T_M(v) \vee T_N(w)$ which implies $T_M(x) \leq T_{N \circ M \circ N}(x)$. Otherwise $x \neq uvw$. Then $T_M(x) \leq 0 = T_{N \circ M \circ N}(x)$. Similarly, we can prove that $I_M(x) \geq I_{N \circ M \circ N}(x)$ and $F_M(x) \leq F_{N \circ M \circ N}(x)$. Thus $X_N \odot X_M \odot X_N \subseteq X_M$.

Conversely, assume that $X_N \odot X_M \odot X_N \subseteq X_M$ for any neutrosophic \aleph -structure X_N .

Let $u, v, w \in X$. If $x = uvw$, then

$$\begin{aligned} T_M(uvw) = T_M(x) &\leq (\chi_X(T)_N \circ T_M \circ \chi_X(T)_N)(x) = \bigwedge_{x=rw} \{ \chi_X(T)_N \circ T_M(r) \vee \chi_X(T)_N(w) \} \\ &= \bigwedge_{x=rc} \{ \bigwedge_{r=uv} \{ \chi_X(T)_N(u) \vee (T)_M(v) \} \vee \chi_X(T)_N(w) \} \\ &\leq \chi_X(T)_N(u) \vee (T)_M(v) \vee \chi_X(T)_N(w) = T_M(v), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_M(uvw) = I_M(x) &\leq (\chi_X(I)_N \circ I_M \circ \chi_X(I)_N)(x) = \bigvee_{x=rw} \{ \chi_X(I)_N \circ I_M(r) \wedge \chi_X(I)_N(w) \} \\ &= \bigvee_{x=rc} \{ \bigvee_{r=uv} \{ \chi_X(I)_N(u) \wedge (I)_M(v) \} \wedge \chi_X(I)_N(w) \} \\ &\geq \chi_X(I)_N(u) \wedge (I)_M(v) \wedge \chi_X(I)_N(w) = (I)_M(v), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} F_M(uvw) = F_M(x) &\leq (\chi_X(F)_N \circ F_M \circ \chi_X(F)_N)(x) = \bigwedge_{x=rw} \{ \chi_X(F)_N \circ F_M(r) \vee \chi_X(F)_N(w) \} \\ &= \bigwedge_{x=rc} \{ \bigwedge_{r=uv} \{ \chi_X(F)_N(u) \vee (F)_M(v) \} \vee \chi_X(F)_N(w) \} \\ &\leq \chi_X(F)_N(u) \vee (F)_M(v) \vee \chi_X(F)_N(w) = F_M(v). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore X_M is neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal. □

Notation 3.19. Let X and Z be semigroups. A mapping $g: X \rightarrow Z$ is said to be a homomorphism if $g(uv) = g(u)g(v)$ for all $u, v \in X$. Throughout this remaining section, we denote $Aut(X)$, the set of all automorphisms of X .

Definition 3.20. An interior ideal J of a semigroup X is called a characteristic interior ideal if $h(J) = J$ for all $h \in Aut(X)$.

Definition 3.21. Let X be a semigroup. A neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal X_N is called neutrosophic \aleph -characteristic interior ideal if $T_N(\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{u})) = T_N(\mathbf{u})$, $I_N(\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{u})) = I_N(\mathbf{u})$ and $F_N(\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{u})) = F_N(\mathbf{u})$ for all $\mathbf{u} \in X$ and all $\mathbf{h} \in \text{Aut}(X)$.

Theorem 3.22. For any $L \subseteq X$, the equivalent assertions are:

- (i) L is characteristic interior ideal,
- (ii) The characteristic neutrosophic \aleph -structure $\chi_L(X_M)$ is neutrosophic \aleph -characteristic interior ideal.

Proof: Suppose L is characteristic interior ideal and let $x \in X$. Then by Theorem 3.1, $\chi_L(X_M)$ is neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal. If $x \in L$, then $\chi_L(T)_M(x) = -1$, $\chi_L(I)_M(x) = 0$, and $\chi_L(F)_M(x) = -1$. Now, for any $h \in \text{Aut}(X)$, $h(x) \in h(L) = L$ which implies $\chi_L(T)_M(h(x)) = -1$, $\chi_L(I)_M(h(x)) = 0$, and $\chi_L(F)_M(h(x)) = -1$. If $x \notin L$, then $\chi_L(T)_M(x) = 0$, $\chi_L(I)_M(x) = -1$, and $\chi_L(F)_M(x) = 0$. Now, for any $h \in \text{Aut}(X)$, $h(x) \notin h(L)$ which implies $\chi_L(T)_M(h(x)) = 0$, $\chi_L(I)_M(h(x)) = -1$, and $\chi_L(F)_M(h(x)) = 0$. Thus $\chi_L(T)_M(h(x)) = \chi_L(T)_M(x)$, $\chi_L(I)_M(h(x)) = \chi_L(I)_M(x)$, and $\chi_L(F)_M(h(x)) = \chi_L(F)_M(x)$ for all $x \in X$ and hence $\chi_L(X_M)$ is neutrosophic \aleph -characteristic interior ideal.

Conversely, assume that $\chi_L(X_M)$ is neutrosophic \aleph -characteristic interior ideal. Then by Theorem 3.1, L is an interior ideal. Now, let $h \in \text{Aut}(X)$ and $x \in L$. Then $\chi_L(T)_M(x) = -1$, $\chi_L(I)_M(x) = 0$ and $\chi_L(F)_M(x) = -1$. Since $\chi_L(X_M)$ is neutrosophic \aleph -characteristic interior ideal, we have $\chi_L(T)_M(h(x)) = \chi_L(T)_M(x)$, $\chi_L(I)_M(h(x)) = \chi_L(I)_M(x)$ and $\chi_L(F)_M(h(x)) = \chi_L(F)_M(x)$ which imply $h(x) \in L$. So $h(L) \subseteq L$ for all $h \in \text{Aut}(X)$. Again, since $h \in \text{Aut}(X)$ and $x \in L$, there exists $y \in L$ such that $h(y) = x$.

Suppose that $y \notin L$. Then $\chi_L(T)_M(y) = 0$, $\chi_L(I)_M(y) = -1$ and $\chi_L(F)_M(y) = 0$. Since $\chi_L(T)_M(h(y)) = \chi_L(T)_M(y)$, $\chi_L(I)_M(h(y)) = \chi_L(I)_M(y)$ and $\chi_L(F)_M(h(y)) = \chi_L(F)_M(y)$, we get $\chi_L(T)_M(h(y)) = 0$, $\chi_L(I)_M(h(y)) = -1$ and $\chi_L(F)_M(h(y)) = 0$ which imply $h(y) \notin L$, a contradiction. So $y \in L$ i.e., $h(y) \in L$. Thus $L \subseteq h(L)$ for all $h \in \text{Aut}(X)$ and hence L is characteristic interior ideal. □

Theorem 3.23. For a semigroup X , the equivalent statements are:

- (i) X is intra-regular,
- (ii) For any neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal X_M , we have $X_M(w) = X_M(w^2)$ for all $w \in X$.

Proof: (i) \Rightarrow (ii) Suppose X is intra-regular, and X_M is neutrosophic \aleph -interior ideal and $w \in X$. Then there exist $r, s \in X$ such that $w = rw^2s$. Now $T_M(w) = T_M(rw^2s) \leq T_M(w^2) \leq T_M(w)$ and so $T_M(w) = T_M(w^2)$, $I_M(w) = I_M(rw^2s) \geq I_M(w^2) \geq I_M(w)$ and so $I_M(w) = I_M(w^2)$, and $F_M(w) = F_M(rw^2s) \leq F_M(w^2) \leq F_M(w)$ and so $F_M(w) = F_M(w^2)$. Therefore $X_M(w) = X_M(w^2)$ for all $w \in X$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i) Let (ii) holds and $s \in X$. Then $I(s^2)$ is an ideal of X . By Theorem 3.5 of [4], $\chi_{I(s^2)}(X_M)$ is neutrosophic \aleph -ideal. By assumption, $\chi_{I(s^2)}(X_M)(s) = \chi_{I(s^2)}(X_M)(s^2)$. Since $\chi_{I(s^2)}(T)_M(s^2) = -1 = \chi_{I(s^2)}(F)_M(s^2)$ and $\chi_{I(s^2)}(I)_M(s^2) = 0$, we get $\chi_{I(s^2)}(T)_M(s) = -1 = \chi_{I(s^2)}(F)_M(s)$ and $\chi_{I(s^2)}(I)_M(s) = 0$ which imply $s \in I(s^2)$. Hence X is intra-regular. □

Theorem 3.24. For a semigroup X , the equivalent statements are:

- (i) X is left (resp., right) regular,

(ii) For any neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -interior ideal X_M , we have $X_M(w) = X_M(w^2)$ for all $w \in X$.

Proof: (i) \Rightarrow (ii) Let X be left regular. Then there exists $y \in X$ such that $w = yw^2$. Let X_M be a neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -interior ideal. Then $T_M(w) = T_M(yw^2) \leq T_M(w)$ and so $T_M(w) = T_M(w^2)$, $I_M(w) = I_M(yw^2) \geq I_M(w)$ and so $I_M(w) = I_M(w^2)$, and $F_M(w) = F_M(yw^2) \leq F_M(w)$ and so $F_M(w) = F_M(w^2)$. Therefore $X_M(w) = X_M(w^2)$ for all $w \in X$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i) Suppose (ii) holds and let X_M be neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -interior ideal. Then for any $w \in X$, $\chi_{L(w^2)}(T)_M(w) = \chi_{L(w^2)}(T)_M(w^2) = -1$, $\chi_{L(w^2)}(I)_M(w) = \chi_{L(w^2)}(I)_M(w^2) = 0$ and $\chi_{L(w^2)}(F)_M(w) = \chi_{L(w^2)}(F)_M(w^2) = -1$ which imply $w \in L(w^2)$. Thus X is left regular. \square

Conclusions

In this paper, we have introduced the concepts of neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -interior ideals and neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -characteristic interior ideals in semigroups and studied their properties, and characterized regular and intra-regular semigroups using neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -interior ideal structures. We have also shown that R is a characteristic interior ideal if and only if the characteristic neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -structure $\chi_R(X_N)$ is neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -characteristic interior ideal. In future, we will define neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -prime ideals in semigroups and study their properties.

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